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ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF CEMENT DUST EXPOSURE ON RENAL BIOMARKERS AMONG CONSTRUCTION WORKERS IN AKALA EXPRESS, IBADAN, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Cement dust exposure is a common occupational hazard among construction workers and may affect renal function through inhalation, dermal contact, and systemic absorption of toxic dust components. This study assessed the impact of cement dust exposure on renal biomarkers among construction workers in Akala Express, Ibadan. A comparative cross-sectional design was adopted. A total of 100 participants were studied, comprising 50 construction workers exposed to cement dust and 50 controls not occupationally exposed to cement dust. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire, while venous blood samples were analyzed for sodium, potassium, chloride, bicarbonate, urea, and creatinine. Descriptive

statistics, independent t-test, and chi-square test were used at a 5% significance level. Exposed workers had significantly higher potassium, urea, and creatinine levels than controls, whereas chloride levels did not differ significantly between groups. Biochemical evidence of kidney dysfunction was observed in 30% of exposed workers and 0% of controls. Weekly exposure duration was significantly associated with kidney dysfunction. The evidence suggests that continuous exposure to cement dust may alter renal biomarkers and recommends routine renal screening, improved dust control, and consistent use of individual protective equipment.

KEYWORDS: Cement Dust; Renal Biomarkers; Construction Workers; Creatinine; Urea; Electrolytes; Occupational Exposure; Akala Express

INTRODUCTION

Environmental and occupational pollution remains an important public health concern as various workplace diseases, which are preventable, continue to cause morbidity and mortality among workers. The International Labour Organization (2015) emphasized the impact of global burden of occupational accidents and diseases, while Krishna *et al.*, (2019) reported dust-exposed workers as an indication that occupational hazards continue to affect workers' health in many developing settings. Construction work is a major economic activity in Nigeria and provides employment for skilled and unskilled labourers; however, the routine handling of cement, sand, concrete, and other building materials can expose workers to respirable dust and chemical particles capable of producing adverse health effects (Adeyanju & Okeke, 2019; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021).

Cement dust is a complex mixture of mineral and chemical particles released during cement production, transport, storage, mixing, and use on construction sites. It contains silica, lime, alumina, calcium oxide, iron oxides, chromium, and other trace substances, and its fine particles may remain suspended in air during dry handling, grinding, drilling, and concrete breaking activities (Mousavi *et al.*, 2014; Sazakli *et al.*, 2014; Dunuweera & Rajapakse, 2018). These particles can enter the body mainly through inhalation, but dermal contact and accidental ingestion may also occur, particularly when workers manually handle cement without adequate personal protective equipment (Al-Salhen, 2014; Li *et al.*, 2019). Crystalline silica and chromium compounds are of particular concern because they have been associated with oxidative stress, inflammation, tissue injury, and whole-body toxicity (Sazakli *et al.*, 2014; Murugadoss *et al.*, 2017).

Although the respiratory effects of cement dust are widely reported, increasing evidence suggests that occupational dust exposure may also affect organs outside the lungs. Inhaled particles can initiate inflammatory and oxidative pathways that may contribute to systemic effects, including possible renal injury (Chen *et al.*, 2018; Honarpisheh, 2020). Studies on silica-related disease have linked chronic exposure to crystalline silica with pulmonary disorders and possible kidney damage, while recent evidence among construction workers has strengthened concern about occupational particle exposure and chronic kidney disease (Hoy & Chambers, 2020; Rees & Murray, 2020; Edlund *et al.*, 2024). Thus, Owonikoko *et al.* (2023) posited that cement dust may therefore be relevant to renal health because some of its constituents can be absorbed into the bloodstream and may contribute to biochemical alterations in kidney function over time

The kidney maintains internal homeostasis by regulating water, acid-base, and electrolyte balance, and by excreting metabolic waste products. Renal biomarkers, such as serum creatinine, urea, sodium, potassium, chloride, and bicarbonate, are widely used to evaluate kidney function and identify early biochemical changes before severe clinical symptoms become apparent (Gounden *et al.*, 2018; Krstic *et al.*, 2016). Serum creatinine and urea provide useful information on renal filtration and nitrogenous waste clearance, while electrolyte measurements help to assess acid-base balance and disturbances that may occur when kidney regulation is impaired (Norris *et al.*, 2018; Ginos & Engberink, 2020; Raphael *et al.*, 2013). In occupational health surveillance, these biomarkers are important because workers exposed to nephrotoxic substances may not present early symptoms, making biochemical screening useful for timely detection and prevention (Jufar *et al.*, 2020; Mizdrak *et al.*, 2022).

Construction workers in Akala Express, Ibadan, are repeatedly exposed to cement dust during routine work activities, including mixing cement, opening cement bags, plastering, blocklaying, breaking concrete, and site cleaning. Many workers operate in open or semi-open environments where dust control measures are inconsistent, while the use of personal protective equipment is often affected by availability, comfort, training, and enforcement. Previous research has shown that construction dust exposure is influenced by task type, exposure duration, ventilation, and adherence to safety practices, and that control measures such as wet methods, respiratory protection, and worker training are key to reducing health risks (Li *et al.*, 2019; Tente, 2023). Despite this, renal health has received less attention than respiratory symptoms in many studies on cement dust exposure, especially among construction workers outside formal cement factory environments (Morshed *et al.*, 2022; Ramadan *et al.*, 2021).

Therefore, this study assessed the impact of occupational exposure to cement dust on selected renal biomarkers among construction workers at Akala Express, Ibadan. The study compared serum electrolytes, urea, and creatinine between workers exposed to cement dust and a control group not occupationally exposed to cement dust. It also examined the relationship between exposure characteristics and biochemical evidence of kidney dysfunction. By providing empirical evidence from a construction worker population, the study contributes to occupational health knowledge and underscores the need for improved dust control, greater use of personal protective equipment, and periodic renal function screening among workers exposed to cement dust.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of the study was to assess the impact of cement dust exposure on renal biomarkers among construction workers in Akala Express, Ibadan. The specific objectives were to:

1. Measure serum levels of kidney parameters, including electrolytes, urea, and creatinine, among workers exposed to cement dust and compare them with control samples;
2. Determine the relationship between cement dust exposure and changes in renal biomarkers among exposed workers.
3. Generate empirical data that can support targeted occupational health interventions and protective actions; and
4. Assess the effectiveness of existing safety practices in reducing the impact of cement dust on renal health.

Hypotheses

The null hypothesis was that there is no significant difference in renal biomarker levels between construction workers exposed to cement dust and unexposed individuals. The alternative hypothesis stated that there is a significant difference in renal biomarker levels between the two groups.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Cement Dust as an Occupational Exposure

Cement dust is a mineral dust generated during the production, transport, storage, and use of cement. In construction environments, it is released when cement bags are opened, when dry cement is poured, when concrete is mixed, and when hardened concrete is cut, drilled, or broken. The risk is higher when work is carried out in dry conditions or without dust suppression. Workers who mix cement manually, carry cement bags, break concrete surfaces, plaster walls, or work close to cement mixers are commonly exposed to visible and respirable dust particles. Unlike factory settings, many construction sites are temporary and may lack fixed ventilation systems, occupational monitoring, and formal health surveillance.

The composition of cement dust explains why it can cause more than local irritation. It contains calcium, silicon, aluminium, iron, and chromium compounds, while respirable crystalline silica is released when cement-based materials are cut or drilled. The fine fraction of the dust can remain suspended in the air and reach the lower respiratory tract when inhaled. From the lungs, inflammatory mediators and some absorbed substances may contribute to systemic effects. Cement dust may also irritate the skin and mucous membranes, particularly when workers handle wet cement without gloves. Therefore, cement dust exposure should be understood as both a respiratory and systemic occupational hazard.

The health burden of occupational dust exposure is particularly relevant in developing countries, where construction work is expanding rapidly, and many workers operate in informal or poorly regulated settings. International concern about occupational diseases has increased because many dust-related conditions are preventable through engineering controls, safe work practices, and personal protective equipment. In Nigeria, construction work remains labor-intensive, and dust exposure may continue for years without regular health checks. This makes local studies important because findings from industrialized settings may not fully reflect exposure realities in Nigerian construction sites.

Routes of Entry and Biological Response to Cement Dust

The main route of cement dust entry into the body is inhalation. Particles inhaled through the nose and mouth may be trapped in the upper airway, but smaller particles can reach the bronchioles and alveoli. When particles persist in lung tissue, they can activate macrophages and epithelial cells, leading to the release of cytokines, reactive oxygen species, and inflammatory mediators. The inflammatory response is initially protective, but repeated exposure may create chronic inflammation and oxidative stress. These processes are important because they can affect organs beyond the lungs through circulating inflammatory signals and absorbed toxic components.

Dermal contact is another route of exposure, especially among workers who mix cement manually or work with wet cement. Cement has alkaline properties and can cause skin irritation or burns. Although dermal exposure is usually discussed in relation to skin disorders, it also reflects poor workplace control and poor use of protective equipment. Accidental ingestion can occur when workers eat, drink, or smoke without washing their hands after handling cement. This route may be less dominant than inhalation, but it remains relevant in settings where hygiene facilities are limited.

The biological effects of cement dust are linked to oxidative stress, inflammation, and possible heavy metal toxicity. Silica particles can stimulate inflammatory pathways and tissue injury. Chromium compounds may contribute to toxicity through oxidative mechanisms and cellular damage. Aluminum and other trace metals may also influence enzyme activity and tissue function. The kidney is vulnerable to these processes because renal tissues receive high blood flow and are involved in filtration and excretion. Repeated low-level exposure may therefore create a gradual burden that is not immediately obvious clinically.

Renal Biomarkers in Occupational Health Surveillance

Renal biomarkers are measurable substances in blood or urine that provide information about kidney function or kidney injury. In routine clinical and occupational practice, serum creatinine and urea are commonly used because they are accessible, relatively inexpensive, and easy to interpret. Creatinine is a waste product of muscle metabolism and is removed mainly by glomerular filtration. Increased serum creatinine may indicate reduced renal filtration, although it can also be influenced by muscle mass, age, and hydration status. Urea is produced by the liver during protein metabolism and excreted by the kidneys. High urea may reflect reduced kidney clearance, dehydration, or increased protein breakdown.

Electrolytes provide additional information on renal function and internal balance. Sodium is important for extracellular fluid volume and osmotic regulation. Potassium is mainly intracellular and is tightly regulated because high serum potassium can affect neuromuscular and cardiac function. Chloride works with sodium and bicarbonate in maintaining osmotic pressure and acid-base balance. Bicarbonate reflects acid-base status and may change in metabolic or respiratory disorders. Because the kidney plays a role in electrolyte regulation, abnormal electrolyte levels may indicate renal stress or disturbed homeostasis.

In occupational health surveillance, renal biomarkers are useful as workers exposed to nephrotoxic substances may not show early symptoms. Regular screening can identify workers who require further assessment or temporary removal from exposure. However, interpretation must be cautious because biomarkers can be influenced by age, sex, hydration, diet, medication use, infection, exercise, and undiagnosed medical conditions. For this reason, comparative studies using exposed and control groups are valuable because they help separate exposure-related patterns from normal population variation.

Cement Dust, Silica, and Renal Health

The relationship between dust exposure and renal health has received increasing attention. Studies on silica and occupational particles suggest that inhaled particles can contribute to kidney injury through inflammatory, immune, and oxidative pathways. Chronic exposure to crystalline silica has

been associated with systemic diseases, including autoimmune responses and kidney-related outcomes. Experimental studies have shown that inhaled silica nanoparticles can cause renal changes in animals, suggesting that respirable particles may have effects beyond the lungs. Although animal findings cannot be directly transferred to humans, they provide biological plausibility for the renal findings observed in exposed workers.

Epidemiological research has also drawn attention to occupational particle exposure and chronic kidney disease (Edlund *et al.*, 2024; Morshed *et al.*, 2022; Sasai *et al.*, 2022; Owonikoko *et al.*, 2023; Tente, 2023). Construction workers may experience mixed exposures involving silica, cement dust, heavy metals, solvents, and heat stress (Lim & Oh, 2023; Möhner, Pohrt, & Gellissen, 2017; Rappaport *et al.*, 1999). The combined effect of these exposures may increase renal burden, especially where workers are dehydrated during long working hours. Heat, physical exertion, and limited access to drinking water may concentrate blood solutes and worsen the effect of dust-related inflammation. This is important for Nigerian construction settings where outdoor work often takes place under hot conditions.

Cement dust exposure is also relevant because cement contains trace elements that may be nephrotoxic at sufficient exposure levels. Chromium, aluminum, and silica have been discussed in relation to oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue damage. The kidney may accumulate or respond to toxic substances through tubular stress and altered filtration. Changes in urea, creatinine, and electrolytes among exposed workers may therefore reflect early renal stress, although they cannot, alone, confirm chronic kidney disease without additional clinical evaluation, such as estimated glomerular filtration rate, urinalysis, or repeated testing.

Previous Studies on Cement Dust and Systemic Effects

Previous studies have repeatedly reported respiratory effects among workers exposed to cement dust. Reduced lung function, chronic cough, phlegm, wheeze, chest tightness, and shortness of breath have been reported among cement factory workers and other dust-exposed groups. These findings are important because they demonstrate that exposure to cement dust can produce measurable biological effects. While respiratory outcomes are most direct, systemic effects may occur when inflammatory mediators and absorbed toxicants enter circulation.

Research on renal outcomes among dust-exposed workers is less extensive than research on respiratory outcomes, but available evidence suggests a possible association. Studies involving silica exposure, cement plant workers, and residents near cement facilities have reported changes in kidney-related biomarkers, including creatinine, urea, urinary enzymes, and albumin. Some authors have reported higher levels of renal biomarkers in exposed groups (Mourad & Ashour, 2020; Jung *et al.*, 2016; Al-Salhen, 2014; Owonikoko *et al.*, 2023), while others have found no statistically significant difference (Sokooti *et al.*, 2017; El-Bendary, Gaber, & Abdel-Hamid, 2018). Such variation may be due to differences in exposure duration, dust concentration, sample size, laboratory methods, use of protective equipment, and other confounding factors.

The inconsistency in previous findings strengthens the need for context-specific research. In settings where workers may not use effective respirators and where dust suppression is irregular, biomarker changes may differ from those in settings with stronger occupational controls. Similarly, construction workers differ from cement factory workers because their exposure is task-

based and may fluctuate daily. Therefore, assessing renal biomarkers among construction workers in Akala Express provides useful local evidence and contributes to a wider understanding of the systemic effects of cement dust.

Determinants of Exposure and Limitations of Protective Measures

The level of cement dust exposure among construction workers depends on several factors. These include the type of task performed, the quantity of cement handled, whether materials are dry or wet, ventilation, weather conditions, distance from dust-generating activities, and the duration of work. Workers involved in mixing, cutting, or demolition are expected to have higher exposure than those performing administrative or supervisory tasks. Weekly exposure duration is also important because repeated exposure within a short period may cause measurable biological stress even when total years of employment are not long.

Personal protective equipment is widely recommended to reduce exposure, but its effectiveness depends on proper selection, fitting, consistent use, and maintenance. Simple cloth masks may reduce visible dust but may not adequately filter respirable particles. Respirators may provide better protection, but they can be uncomfortable in hot environments and may be unavailable or unaffordable for informal workers. Workers may also remove masks during strenuous tasks because of heat, sweating, and breathing discomfort. Therefore, self-reported use of protective measures does not always mean an effective reduction in exposure.

Engineering controls such as wet methods, local exhaust ventilation, enclosed mixing points, and dust suppression are more reliable than personal protection alone. However, such controls are often limited on small construction sites. Administrative measures, including training, task rotation, rest breaks, hygiene facilities, and regular medical screening, can further reduce risk. A comprehensive prevention strategy should therefore combine engineering controls, administrative controls, and appropriate personal protective equipment, rather than relying solely on masks.

Research Gap

Although cement dust exposure is a recognized occupational hazard, many studies in Nigeria and other similar settings have focused mainly on respiratory symptoms and lung function. Less attention has been paid to renal biomarkers among construction workers, especially those working outside factory environments. There is also limited local evidence on how weekly exposure duration, years of exposure, and protective practices relate to indicators of kidney dysfunction.

The present study addresses this gap by comparing serum electrolytes, urea, and creatinine between construction workers exposed to cement dust and a control group not occupationally exposed. It also examines the association between exposure characteristics and biochemical evidence of kidney dysfunction. The study is useful for occupational health planning because simple renal biomarkers can be incorporated into routine screening programs for workers who regularly handle cement.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Study Area

A comparative cross-sectional research design was used to assess renal biomarkers among construction workers exposed to cement dust and a control group not occupationally exposed to

cement dust. The study was carried out at Akala Express, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, an area with active construction and regular use of cement-based materials.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population consisted of construction workers at Akala Express, who were routinely exposed to cement dust, and a control group of individuals from a similar demographic background who were not occupationally exposed to cement dust. A total of 100 participants were included, comprising 50 exposed workers and 50 controls. Random sampling was used to select participants from both groups.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Participants in the exposed group were active construction workers aged 18 to 60 years who had worked in construction for at least one year and had no known kidney disease at the time of the study. Control participants were individuals of similar age and demographic characteristics who did not work in construction and were not occupationally exposed to cement dust. Individuals with known kidney disease, serious health conditions that could influence renal biomarkers, or recent exposure to other environmental pollutants were excluded.

Instrument for Data Collection

A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data on sociodemographic characteristics, work history, job role, duration and frequency of cement dust exposure, use of personal protective equipment, health history, and safety practices. The questionnaire also obtained information on lifestyle factors such as alcohol use and smoking history.

Blood Sample Collection and Laboratory Analysis

Five milliliters of venous blood sample were collected from each participant into lithium heparin bottles for the estimation of electrolytes, urea, and creatinine. Sodium was estimated using a selective chromogen method; potassium by reaction with sodium tetraphenylboron; chloride by ferric thiocyanate formation; and bicarbonate by an enzymatic reaction involving phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase and malate dehydrogenase. Urea was estimated by enzymatic hydrolysis and color development, while creatinine was estimated using the alkaline picrate reaction. Absorbance readings were taken spectrophotometrically according to the relevant laboratory procedures.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Review Ethical Committee of the Oyo State Ministry of Health, Ibadan, with assigned number NHREC/OYOSHRIEC/10/11/22. Participants were informed of the study's purpose before participating. Written informed consent was obtained, while verbal consent was obtained from participants who could not read or write after the study was explained to them in a language they understood. Personal data were anonymized to maintain confidentiality.

Statistical Analysis

Data from questionnaires and laboratory assays were entered into Microsoft Excel, checked for entry errors, and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarise demographic and occupational variables. An independent t-test was used to compare mean renal biomarker levels between groups, while a chi-square test was used to examine associations between categorical variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Demographic and Occupational Characteristics of Participants

A total of 100 participants were included in the study. The exposed group comprised 50 construction workers, of whom 27 were male and 23 were female. The control group also comprised 50 participants, of whom 29 were male and 21 were female. Among exposed workers, the largest proportion reported five hours of weekly exposure to cement particles. Most participants with exposure had 4-6 years of exposure, and 66% reported using protective measures.

Table 1: Demographic and occupational characteristics of participants

Gender			0.162	0.6873
Male	27 (54%)	29 (58%)		
Female	23 (46%)	21 (42%)		
Weekly exposure to cement particles		NA		
One hour	6 (12%)	NA		
Two hours	9 (18%)	NA		
Five hours	22 (44%)	NA		
Ten hours	13 (26%)	NA		
Length of exposure to cement particles		NA		
1-3 years	11 (22%)	NA		
4-6 years	17 (34%)	NA		
7-9 years	14 (28%)	NA		
10 years and above	8 (16%)	NA		
Use of protective measures		NA		

Yes	33 (66%)	NA		
No	17 (34%)	NA		

Note: NA = Not applicable.

Comparison of Renal Biomarkers Between Exposed and Control Groups

The exposed group had a mean sodium level of 141.55 mmol/L compared with 140.16 mmol/L among controls, with no statistically significant difference. Potassium was significantly higher in the exposed group than in the control group. Chloride also differed significantly between groups, whereas bicarbonate did not. Urea and creatinine were significantly higher among exposed workers, suggesting possible renal stress or reduced renal clearance.

Table 2: Comparative analysis of serum electrolyte, urea, and creatinine parameters between exposed workers and the control group

Sodium (Na) (mmol/L)	141.55 +/- 6.175	140.16 +/- 6.335	1.11	0.270
Potassium (K) (mmol/L)	4.07 +/- 0.514	3.52 +/- 0.732	4.37	0.000*
Chloride (Cl-) (mmol/L)	106.54 +/- 6.656	118.32 +/- 23.970	-3.35	0.001*
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻) (mmol/L)	26.99 +/- 4.731	27.99 +/- 4.639	-1.07	0.290
Urea (mg/dL)	34.85 +/- 15.728	27.25 +/- 7.859	3.06	0.003*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.32 +/- 0.807	0.89 +/- 0.387	3.38	0.001*

Note: * Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Percentage of Kidney Dysfunction

Biochemical evidence of kidney dysfunction was observed among 15 of the 50 exposed workers, representing 30%. None of the control participants had biochemical results indicative of kidney dysfunction. This finding suggests a higher burden of renal biomarker alteration among workers occupationally exposed to cement dust.

Table 3: Percentage of kidney dysfunction among exposed and control groups

Exposed group	50	15	35	30
Control group	50	0	50	0

Source: Laboratory analysis from the study.

Comparison of Biochemical Markers Based on Kidney Dysfunction Status

Participants whose biochemical results indicated kidney dysfunction had significantly higher potassium, urea, and creatinine levels than those whose results did not. Sodium, chloride, and bicarbonate did not show statistically significant differences. This pattern suggests that potassium, urea, and creatinine were the most responsive markers of kidney dysfunction in the present study.

Table 4: Comparison of biochemical markers between individuals with and without kidney dysfunction

Sodium (Na) (mmol/L)	141.7 +/- 6.0	139.2 +/- 4.6	1.74	0.092
Potassium (K) (mmol/L)	4.34 +/- 0.7	3.87 +/- 0.3	2.77	0.008*
Chloride (Cl-) (mmol/L)	106.4 +/- 7.6	103.2 +/- 6.2	1.82	0.074
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻) (mmol/L)	26.1 +/- 6.3	24.5 +/- 3.2	1.35	0.181
Urea (mg/dL)	37.3 +/- 16.6	26.0 +/- 7.4	3.35	0.002*
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.38 +/- 0.6	0.99 +/- 0.2	3.97	0.000*

Note: * Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Association Between Degree of Exposure and Kidney Dysfunction

Weekly exposure to cement particles was significantly associated with kidney dysfunction. Workers exposed for longer weekly periods had more cases of kidney dysfunction than workers with lower weekly exposure. However, length of exposure in years and reported use of protective measures were not significantly associated with kidney dysfunction in this study.

Table 5: Association between degree of exposure and kidney dysfunction

Weekly exposure to cement particles			4.115	0.041*
One hour	2	13		
Two hours	3	9		
Five hours	5	6		
Ten hours	5	7		
Length of exposure to cement particles			1.598	0.206
1-3 years	6	11		
4-6 years	5	9		
7-9 years	1	6		
10 years and above	3	9		
Use of protective measures			0.797	0.384
Yes	7	21		
No	8	14		

Note: * Significant at $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

This study assessed the impact of cement dust exposure on renal biomarkers among construction workers in Akala Express, Ibadan. The major finding was that construction workers exposed to cement dust had significant alterations in selected renal biomarkers when compared with the control group. Potassium, urea, and creatinine were significantly higher among exposed workers, while chloride also showed a significant difference between the two groups. These findings suggest that cement dust exposure may be associated with renal stress or early biochemical changes among exposed workers.

The finding of significantly higher potassium among exposed workers is important because potassium is tightly regulated by the kidney. Although the mean potassium level in the exposed group was not extremely high, the significant difference from controls shows a shift in electrolyte balance. The kidney normally removes excess potassium from the body, and impaired renal

excretion can lead to elevated serum potassium levels. In occupational settings, an increase in potassium may reflect early renal dysfunction, dehydration, or other metabolic stressors. Construction workers often perform physically demanding tasks, and when these tasks are combined with dust exposure and poor hydration, electrolyte imbalance is more likely.

Urea and creatinine were also significantly higher among exposed workers. These two markers are widely used in routine kidney function assessment because they reflect renal clearance of metabolic waste products. Elevated urea may occur when kidney filtration is reduced, but it may also be influenced by hydration, protein intake, and catabolic state. Creatinine is generally considered a more stable marker of glomerular filtration than urea, although it is also influenced by muscle mass and age. The significant increase in both urea and creatinine among exposed workers strengthens the possibility that cement dust exposure or related occupational conditions may contribute to renal stress.

The observed pattern is consistent with studies linking occupational dust and silica exposure to kidney-related effects, including reports of elevated renal biomarkers among workers exposed to cement dust and silica (Mourad & Ashour, 2020; Jung *et al.*, 2016; Möhner, Pohrt, & Gellissen, 2017). Cement dust contains silica and other trace elements that can stimulate inflammation and oxidative stress. Inhaled particles can activate immune responses in the lungs, and persistent inflammation may have systemic consequences. Experimental evidence has also shown that inhaled silica particles can produce renal changes, suggesting biological plausibility for kidney involvement. In addition, occupational studies have reported changes in renal markers among workers exposed to silica, cement dust, or multiple construction-related hazards. The current findings therefore fit within a growing body of evidence that dust exposure may affect organs beyond the respiratory system.

The significantly lower chloride level in the exposed group compared with the control group requires careful interpretation. Chloride is involved in fluid balance and acid-base regulation, and it often changes in relation to sodium and bicarbonate. The difference observed in this study may reflect altered electrolyte balance, hydration status, or other physiological differences between the two groups. Because bicarbonate did not differ significantly, the chloride finding should not be interpreted alone as definite renal disease. Instead, it should be considered together with the significant changes in potassium, urea, and creatinine.

Sodium and bicarbonate did not show significant differences between exposed and control groups. This may be because these parameters are tightly regulated and may remain within normal limits until kidney dysfunction becomes more advanced. It is also possible that the sample size was insufficient to detect mild differences in these markers. The absence of significant changes in sodium and bicarbonate does not rule out renal stress, because kidney dysfunction can begin with changes in waste product clearance or in selected electrolyte handling before all markers become abnormal.

The study found that 30% of exposed workers had biochemical evidence of kidney dysfunction, whereas none of the control participants did. This difference is meaningful from an occupational health perspective because it indicates that a substantial proportion of exposed workers may already have abnormal renal findings. Even if these abnormalities are early or mild, they should not be ignored, as continued exposure may increase the risk of progression. Routine renal

screening can identify affected workers and encourage timely medical evaluation, health education, and exposure reduction.

The association between weekly exposure duration and kidney dysfunction is one of the strongest findings of this study. Workers with longer weekly exposure had more cases of kidney dysfunction than workers with lower weekly exposure. This suggests a possible dose-response pattern, where more frequent or longer exposure to cement dust is associated with greater renal biomarker alteration. A dose-response relationship supports the argument that exposure intensity matters. It also shows that the current work pattern may be as important as total years of employment when evaluating occupational risk.

Length of exposure in years was not significantly associated with kidney dysfunction. This result may appear unexpected because long-term exposure is often assumed to increase risk. However, years of work alone may not accurately measure the actual dust dose. A worker who has spent ten years in construction but performs tasks with low dust exposure may have less cumulative exposure than a worker who has spent four years mixing cement daily. Similarly, workers may change job roles over time, and past exposure may not be well remembered. Therefore, weekly exposure duration may have been a more direct indicator of recent dust burden in this study than total years in construction.

Reported use of protective measures was not significantly associated with kidney dysfunction. This finding should not be taken to mean that protective measures are unimportant. Rather, it may reflect the difference between reported use and effective use. Some workers may use simple masks that do not adequately filter respirable particles. Others may wear masks irregularly, remove them during strenuous work, reuse damaged masks, or wear them incorrectly. Protective equipment also works best when combined with engineering controls such as wet methods and improved ventilation. Therefore, the non-significant association may indicate poor-quality or inconsistent use of protection rather than the absence of a benefit.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that construction workers exposed to cement dust in Akala Express, Ibadan, had significant alterations in selected renal biomarkers compared with controls who were not occupationally exposed to cement dust. Potassium, urea, and creatinine were significantly higher among exposed workers, while chloride also differed significantly between the exposed and control groups. These results indicate that cement dust exposure may contribute to renal stress or early renal dysfunction among construction workers.

The study further showed that biochemical evidence of kidney dysfunction was present in 30% of exposed workers and absent among controls. The duration of weekly exposure to cement particles was significantly associated with kidney dysfunction, suggesting that time spent in dust-generating work may influence renal biomarker changes. However, years of exposure and reported use of protective measures were not significantly associated with kidney dysfunction, possibly because they did not fully capture actual dust dose or effective protection.

Overall, the findings support the need to include renal health in occupational surveillance for construction workers. Cement dust exposure should not be viewed only from the perspective of

respiratory disease; its possible systemic effects should also be addressed. Routine screening, safer work practices, improved dust control, and proper use of effective respiratory protection are necessary to reduce the risk of renal impairment among workers who regularly handle cement.

Implication of Study

The findings have important implications for construction site management. First, cement dust should not be treated as mere nuisance dust. It should be considered a potential systemic hazard that may affect kidney function in addition to respiratory health. Second, employers and site supervisors should move beyond merely advising workers to wear masks. They should provide appropriate respirators, ensure proper fit, reduce dust generation at the source, and make clean water available. Third, periodic health screening should include renal biomarkers, especially for workers involved in cement mixing, cutting, and demolition.

The study also has implications for public health and occupational regulation. Many construction workers in Nigeria work in informal or semi-formal arrangements where occupational health services are limited. Without regular screening, workers may only seek care when symptoms are advanced. Simple laboratory tests such as urea, creatinine, and electrolytes can be used as part of basic surveillance. Where abnormal results are found, workers can be referred for further evaluation, including repeat testing, urinalysis, and estimated glomerular filtration rate. This would help prevent avoidable progression to more serious kidney problems.

Limitations and Strengths of the Study

The results must be interpreted with some caution. The study used a cross-sectional design, meaning exposure and biomarkers were measured at a single point in time. Therefore, causality cannot be firmly established. The study also did not include direct environmental dust measurements, so individual exposure levels were based on occupational history and self-reported exposure. In addition, renal biomarkers can be influenced by hydration, diet, medication, infection, age, sex, muscle mass, and lifestyle factors. Although the control group helped to improve comparison, these potential confounders may still have influenced the results.

In spite of these limitations, the study delivers useful evidence from a local construction environment. It shows that renal biomarker changes exist among cement dust-exposed workers and that weekly exposure time is associated with kidney dysfunction. The study also demonstrates the value of simple biochemical testing in occupational health research. Future studies should include larger sample sizes, personal dust monitoring, repeated biomarker measurements, and more sensitive renal injury markers such as urinary albumin, N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase, or beta-2 microglobulin. Longitudinal studies would be especially useful because they can show whether workers with abnormal biomarkers continue to worsen with ongoing exposure or improve after exposure reduction.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested;

1. Construction companies and site supervisors should strengthen dust control practices, including wet methods, adequate ventilation, enclosed mixing points and safer cement handling procedures.

2. Workers should be provided with appropriate personal protective equipment such as well-fitting dust masks or respirators, and they should receive regular training on correct use, cleaning, storage, and replacement.
3. Routine renal function screening should be conducted for construction workers who are repeatedly exposed to cement dust, especially workers with prolonged weekly exposure or those involved in cement mixing, cutting and demolition.
4. Health education should be provided to workers on the possible respiratory and systemic effects of cement dust exposure, the importance of hydration and the need for early medical assessment when symptoms or abnormal test results occur.
5. Regulatory agencies should enforce occupational health standards on construction sites and encourage documentation of exposure control measures, accident records, training activities, and health surveillance results.
6. Future studies should include environmental dust monitoring, larger sample sizes, longitudinal follow-up, and more sensitive renal injury markers to strengthen evidence on the relationship between cement dust exposure and kidney function.

Declarations

Ethical approval: Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Review Ethical Committee of the Oyo State Ministry of Health, Ibadan. Assigned number: NHREC/OYOSHRIEC/10/11/22.

Consent to participate: Informed consent was obtained from all participants before sample collection and questionnaire administration.

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Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability: The data are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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